

Studying the Application of Deep Learning to the Task of Key Estimation

Blai Meléndez Catalán

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Master thesis supervisor

Emilia Gómez

Department of Information and Communication Technologies

Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona

Dedicat a la família i les amistats.

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Abstract

In this thesis, we present, analyse and evaluate two approaches to the music information retrieval (MIR) task of audio key estimation using neural networks and basic deep learning techniques. Although the task has been addressed many times before and with a large variety of methods, few attempts have been made using this increasingly popular machine learning option. Through several experiments, we extract conclusions about the limitations of some of the current approaches, about what is relevant to key estimation and about the ways in which deep learning can successfully be applied to estimate key. We also set a few accuracy baselines in order to evaluate their performance and validate these conclusions. Our approaches surpass the template-based methods used in some MIR libraries such as Essentia, but struggle with a powerful machine learning techniques such as SVM. Finally, to put the acquired knowledge to use, we include a proposal for a hypothetical third approach in the future work section, specifying its most important features.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Key is an essential concept of music that matters both to musicians, as it is related with style, structure or rhythm, and to naive listeners, because it is a powerful mood inducer. The automatic estimation of key from audio or symbolic information has been a research in the Musical Information Retrieval (MIR) field for more than a decade. In the literature, the methods and algorithms applied to key estimation have evolved dramatically; however, almost no attempt have been carried out yet using deep learning techniques, which lately have been acquiring a lot of relevance in the machine learning domain after becoming state of the art in many topics. Hence, our motivation is to venture into the task of key estimation using these techniques. That is why, throughout this investigation, we will be extracting conclusions from our experiments and the experience and knowledge gathered, to be able to propose future ways in which deep learning can be applied to be more successful in the task of key estimation. This constitutes our most important goal.

On another note, a very recurrent argument against deep neural networks is the incapacity to know what they are actually learning from the data that we provide them with. We assume that it is possible for them to carry out an acceptable classification of this data based on features extracted from it that have little or nothing to do with the actual classification task. Therefore, as a secondary goal, we want to build an architecture that enables us to understand, through its analysis after the training and the results that it offers to testing, what the network is learning. Specifically, we are interested to know if what it learns has a musical meaning related to the task we built the network for. Finally, a third and more ambitious goal is to create a network that produces state of the art results.

2. STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Key

Key is an essential concept in tonal music that defines the relationship between pitch classes and guides the listener to a particular way of perceiving the musical elements such as notes and chords based on their stability and appropriateness [1]. Key is also very important in western music as its modulation is related to other basic concepts such as rhythm, structure or style, and works as a powerful mood inducer.

2.2 Audio key estimation

The task of key estimation has been addressed from different points of view, using a variety of evolving features and techniques, and even in combination with other MIR tasks. In spite of their differences, almost all algorithms are based on four general steps: First, a frequency analysis of an audio is performed; then, an attempt to match its frequency content to a number of pitch classes follows; after that, features that represent this content are generated; and finally, this representation is used to estimate key of the audio.

Figure 1 General steps for the task of key estimation.

The list of features used for this task is long and still growing [2]; however, the most popular are probably those related to the concept of Pitch Class Profile (PCP), which was introduced in the first attempt to estimate the key of a musical piece from symbolic information [3]. A PCP was originally defined as a 12-dimensional vector containing the relative duration for which each note is played in a MIDI file. To estimate key, this vector is correlated with major and minor profiles obtained through the Probe Tone Method [4]. These vectors are of the same dimensions as the PCP and represent the tonal importance, based on listener experience, of each note in the chromatic scale for a generic key. A ring-shift of these vectors is required to obtain the profile for each particular key root. The number of shifts for which the correlation achieves the highest value indicates the key of the piece.

The way the PCPs are computed changed many times in the literature [1], [5]–[8], as research experimented with them in order to adapt them to new challenges such as key estimation in polyphonic music. The Harmonic Pitch Class Profile (HPCP) or chroma [9] is an example of that, as the profile values take into account not only the relative duration but also the relative intensity of each pitch class, as well as the presence of harmonics and the chord hierarchy.

The characteristic that all of these approaches share is that they estimate key through the correlation of the extracted features with a key profile; that is why they are called correlation- or template-based methods. This kind of approaches, however, have two strong limitations: the first one is that while a particular key profile might be able to offer decent classification results for a certain musical genre, there is no single key profile that allows us to maintain this level of performance for different genres or even for different datasets of the same genre. The second limitation comes from the lack of flexibility of a static profile, which will never allow the correct classification of some of the most unusual songs in its corresponding genre or dataset, effectively creating a limit for its accuracy.

Figure 2 Key profile for the A major key (left). HPCP of the song “D.A.N.C.E.” from Justice, written in the key of A major (right).

Key can be estimated for the whole duration of a musical piece or for segments of it. Contemporary musical styles such as pop and rock normally use only one key per song; however, in the classical genre, music pieces are written in a particular key, which is usually stated in the name of the composition, but include several modulations that provide harmonic complexity. This makes it interesting to analyse key from both a local [10]–[13] and a global [9], [14]–[16] perspective. The first one requires a segmentation process, but achieves a higher precision in the description of key. The second one is easier to compute, as it does not need any segmentation and is based on more information; however, it omits possible modulations, and therefore, provides a poorer analysis.

The information about the chords contained in a musical piece, and the sequences they form, is very relevant when trying to identify its key as well as key is very helpful to have a general idea of what chords might appear in it. This tight relationship between them can be exploited in two ways: simultaneously [12], [17], which provides a general view of the composition helping to avoid suboptimal results due to mistakes in the early decisions, or sequentially [18], [19]. In this last case, it is clearly one of the tasks that benefits from the other, for instance, as an additional feature for the estimations.

The machine learning technique that has been applied the most to the task of key estimation is the Hidden Markov Models (HMM) [13], [20]. The hidden states represent the possible keys, which are fully connected by the transition probabilities from one key to another. The main difference between algorithms is what they consider an observation. For instance, in [20] an observation is emitted only when a change of chords happens and a probability is derived from that pair of chords. In [13] there is an observation at every frame that consists in a 24-dimensional chromagram vector and the probability is computed based on the cosine distance between this observation and a pre-defined key template. Comparisons between cognitive-based and machine learning methods [9], [21] conclude that the difference in performance is quite low and that there is no algorithm that emerges as clearly better than the others. This is partly due to the comparison difficulty that arises from the usage of different datasets, amounts of data and evaluation criteria.

To solve that, MIREX established official evaluation metrics for many MIR tasks. In the case of key estimation, each correctly detected key is always rewarded with a full point, but not all incorrect predictions are worth 0 points: if the perfect fifth, the major or minor relative or the parallel key are detected instead of the correct one, a score of 0.5, 0.3 and 0.2 is granted, respectively. Additionally, MIREX keeps secret testing datasets to fairly evaluate the performance of all the algorithms presented to its competitions.

2.3 Deep learning

Deep learning is not a new branch of the field of machine learning as its first steps date from 1971 [22]; however, it was not until 2006 [23] that it emerged as a viable technique for real applications. Nowadays, it has been applied to many different fields such as computer vision, speech recognition, natural language processing, bioinformatics, music information retrieval, etc., and it is the best attempt of machine learning to move towards Artificial Intelligence, which is one of its original goals [24].

Figure 3 Deep neural network with 3 hidden layers. Image from <http://neuralnetworksanddeeplearning.com/chap6.html>, last checked 10/08/2016.

Systems based on deep learning try to make sense of raw data such as images, sound or text typically using Deep Neural Networks (DNN), which are a type of Artificial Neural Networks that stack many hidden layers instead of just one, and thus, are “deeper”. Starting from the input layer, each subsequent layer theoretically corresponds to a higher level of abstraction and contains representations that are formed from those of

lower levels in a hierarchical way. These layers consist of several simple processors called “neurons” that may or may not produce a real-valued output named “activation” according to a given input and a non-linear function¹. All neurons of a particular layer m are connected to all the neurons of the previous and next layers, $m - 1$ and $m + 1$, respectively, except for the input and output layers. All the values coming from layer $m - 1$ are considered the input for layer m and all information produced by layer m form the input for layer $m + 1$. Each of the connections between layers possesses a particular weight that multiplies the output produced by the neurons when they are activated. These weights are the parameters that are adjusted through training in order for the network to show the desired behaviour [25].

Figure 4 A neuron from the inside. $W_{j,i}$ are the connections' weights while g is the non-linear function. Image from <http://www.slideshare.net/JrgenSandig/neural-networks-and-deep-learning>, last check 10/08/2016.

Many variations of this basic DNN structure have been created to better adapt to the requirements of different tasks. The most common are the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [26] and the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The CNN may come alone or complement a regular DNN as an initial section and is mainly used with two-dimensional inputs. The structure of this type of neural network is composed by one or more alternations of two different types of layers: a convolution and a max-pooling layer. In the first layer, the connections between one neuron of layer m and the neurons in layer $m - 1$ are restricted to a local subset that usually spans in both axes of the input. Additionally, there are various groups of neurons that share the same connection's weights and cover all the extension of the input in what effectively is a convolution with the filter being the connection's weights.

Figure 5 Example of a Convolutional Neural Network. Image from [27] p. 454 (modified)

¹ "Activation function," in *Wikipedia: The Free Encyclopedia*; (Wikimedia Foundation Inc., updated 31 March 2016, 08:35 UTC) [encyclopedia on-line]; available from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Activation_function#Comparison_of_activation_functions; Internet; retrieved 07 April 2016.

A feature map is obtained after applying a non-linear function to the output value of every neuron of a particular group. In the second layer, this feature map is max-pooled by a certain factor. This max-pooling operation and the fact that many weights are shared contribute to a reduction of the number of parameters to optimize, making the training computationally much faster. Its way of functioning makes the CNNs especially convenient to work with strongly correlated and invariant data.

The main difference between RNN and DNN is that the recurrent version allows connections between neurons of the same layer, effectively introducing the memory from previous steps in the output of the current step, which provides the network with the ability to model temporal dependencies. There can be as many layers as wanted with this kind of connections with a minimum of one. There are quite a lot of types of RNN; one of the most successful [28] is the Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM) [29] which incorporate a different sort of neurons that solves an inherent weakness of the regular RNN: the phenomenon known as vanishing/exploding gradient [30].

Figure 6 Example of Recurrent Neural Network with 2 recurrent layers. Image from <http://cs.stanford.edu/people/karpathy/recurrentjs/>, last checked 10/08/2016.

The training process of a DNN usually starts with the initialization of its weights [31] to values that hopefully are close to those we need for our task reducing the number of iterations needed to reach them. This initialization can be performed through the pre-training of the network either with Deep Belief Networks (DBN) [23], or Autoencoders (AE) [32] or even using probability distribution functions [31] among other possibilities [33]. After that, the network is trained in a supervised way using the data in the training set. The process consists in updating the weights of the network's connections through algorithms such as the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimization according to a cost function and the error propagated by the Backpropagation (BP) method [34]. There are many parameters that influence the performance of the training: The learning rate, which sets the pace at which the weights are updated; the momentum, which determines the influence of previous gradients on the current step; the number of training instances per mini-batch, i.e., after how many instances and update of the weights is carried out; the number of epochs, which is the number of times we present the whole training set to the network; regularization factors [35] such as the dropout [36] or other techniques such as early stopping [37] that help preventing over-fitting; and also the type of non-linear function used in the neurons [38], [39].

2.4 Deep learning approaches in music information retrieval

We have explained before that DNNs are very good at finding hierarchical dependencies between concepts of different levels of abstraction inside raw data. The usually hierarchical nature of music [40] is, therefore, a plus to think that deep learning techniques might suit the field of MIR. In fact, they have already been applied to many tasks related to the retrieval of music information. Some of the most relevant are onset [41], [42], and boundary [43], [44], detection, beat tracking [45] and tempo estimation [46], chord recognition [27], [47]–[50] and key estimation [51], classification of musical instruments [52] and genres [51], [53], music recommendation [54], source separation [55], [56], note transcription [57], etc.

In spite of everything, the field of deep learning is indeed very young, open and still fairly unexplored, hence, there is a lot of room for innovation and no established best path to do things. Effectively, the variety of options and approaches in very important aspects such as the selection of features, and especially the size and architecture of the DNN provide researchers with much freedom, but also reflects the current uncertainty about their impact on the results. Nonetheless, there seems to be trends in other facets such as the type of network, the pre-processing techniques or the training and evaluation methods.

Regarding the features, it is most common to manually engineer them. Usually, a two-dimensional array formed by the concatenation, in time, of a frequency representation of each subsequent audio frame is used. The diversity in the engineered features comes mainly from the type of frequency representation chosen. For instance, many different numbers of Mel-bands [41]–[43] have been used in order to achieve a more perceptual frequency representation of the audio data. There are tasks like source separation that tend to rely only on the raw spectrogram [55], [56], while in other occasions it proves useful to accompany it with phase information [52] or to filter it in bands that are considered to be meaningful for a particular purpose [45], [46], [57]. The constant Q transform [47]–[50] has been applied to tasks such as chord recognition where notes are very relevant. Other possibilities include chroma features and timbre descriptors [51], MFCCs [54] or Self-Similarity Lag matrices [44].

The engineered features normally require some extra pre-processing techniques to be applied to them, in order to better adapt to the task at hand and enhance performance, before being used as input for the DNN. The most common is the max-pooling operation between adjacent frames to provide a temporal context to the DNN [39], [42]–[44], [47]–[49], [55]. Normalization [41][43][44][48] is also popular and usually transforms the features in order for them to have zero mean and unit variance. Reducing dimensionality is another purpose of the pre-processing, for which methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [47], [48], [54] are used. Limiting the frequency range of the representation [43], [44], [46]–[48], [50] or down-sampling the audio data [48], [50], [54] are alternative ways to reduce the dimensionality of features, which leads to less parameters to be optimized during training.

CNNs [41], [43], [44], [48], [50]–[54], [56] and RNNs [42], [45]–[47], [49], [55], [57] are much more popular for MIR tasks than the regular DNNs. The aforementioned two-dimensional array sort of features has a strong correlation in both axis and is invariant in the temporal dimension and, depending on the representation, also in the frequency

dimension, which makes CNNs a very suitable option. In the case of the RNNs, it is the sequential nature of music that established them as an appropriate candidate. Additionally, both of them have the ability to incorporate contextual information using filters that span in the temporal dimension and modelling temporal dependencies, respectively.

Table 1 Principal characteristics of deep learning approaches to MIR tasks.

Tasks	Features	Pre-processing	Type of network	Classifier
Onset detection	Mel-bands	Pooling, Normalization	CNN, RNN	Threshold
Boundary detection	Mel-bands	Pooling, Normalization, Limited freq. range	CNN	Threshold
Beat tracking	Band-filtered Spectrogram	-	RNN	-
Tempo estimation	Band-filtered Spectrogram	Limited freq. range	RNN	Threshold, Softmax
Chord recognition	Constant – Q transform	Pooling, Normalization, PCA, Limited freq. range	CNN, RNN	Argmax, Softmax, HMM, SVM, HBS, GMM
Key estimation	Chroma and timbre descriptors	-	CNN	-
Instrument classification	Spectrogram and phase information	-	CNN	Softmax
Genre classification	Chroma and timbre descriptors	-	CNN	Argmax, Logistic regression
Music recommendation	MFCC	PCA, Down-sampling	CNN	-
Source separation	Spectrogram	-	CNN, RNN	-
Note transcription	Band-filtered Spectrogram	-	RNN	Logistic regression

The DNNs and their variants can be understood, sometimes, as a way to create a set of features that meet the requirements of the task at hand better than the features that are provided as their input and that we have listed before. The fact is that, in these cases, the created features are still features and not an estimation or any kind of final result for the task; therefore, they need to be translated into a class, and that is why a classifier is needed. The classifier used in the literature can be as simple as a threshold [41]–[44],

[46], an argmax [50], [53] or a softmax operation [46], [48], [52], or more complex machine learning techniques such as a Logistic Regression [51], [57], a Random Forest [39], a Hashed Beam Search [49], an HMM [48], an SVM [48] or a GMM [27].

We have already explained how training works in the previous subsection. The parameters used for the training as well as the evaluation methods and the datasets are very specific to each task and even to each approach to the same task. That is why we only detail this information for the key estimation and chord recognition tasks in the next subsection as they are the most relevant to our work.

2.5 Deep learning for key and chord estimation

Even though this thesis' topic is about studying the application of deep learning to the task of key estimation, in this section we also provide a summary of several papers that cover research about the usage of this machine learning technique to chord recognition. We do this for three reasons: First, the main difference between tonality and chords is a matter of temporal scale; second, we have found only one paper that investigated the first topic, while more researchers have addressed the second one; and third, as we have seen, chord recognition can help in the key estimation process. A detailed description of three approaches to chord recognition and one to key estimation follow.

Regarding the chord recognition task, there seems to be quite an agreement in using a two dimensional array formed by a concatenation in time of a number of constant Q coefficients [27], [48], [50] as the time-frequency representation of the audio data. In these approaches, a down-sampling operation of the original audio signal precedes the transformation in order to increase frequency resolution and the frequency representation is truncated to upper and lower bounds to reduce dimensionality by discarding non-relevant frequency regions. With the same purpose, PCA is applied in [48] as well as a normalization process of the mean and the variance.

In [50], several architectures for a CNN with different combinations of filters are studied. Taking advantage of the frequency invariance of the constant Q representation, data augmentation is applied by shifting the input in the frequency dimension from 1 to 12 semitones effectively multiplying the amount of training data by a factor of 12. For training, mini-batch SGD and BP with a Negative log-likelihood loss function is performed. The classification consists in a simple argmax operation and the datasets involved are the Beatles, RWC Pop and US Pop datasets, which amount to a total of 475 music recordings. Evaluation is carried out with a 5-fold cross validation using 60 % of the data for training, 20 % for the validation and 20 % for testing. Additionally, early stopping is applied. The best accuracy reaches 77.48 %.

The CNN in [27], which consists in 2 convolutional and 3 fully-connected layers, is trained to simultaneously learn the 6-dimensions Tonnetz projection or tonal centroid [58] and a unidimensional null-chord regressor using mini-batch SGD and BP with a regularization factor and an adapted loss function. To classify the output of the network, it is supplied to a multivariate Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM). The audio data consists of 493 chord-annotated polyphonic sound recordings including the Beatles, Queen, RWC Pop and the US Pop datasets. A 13-fold cross validation is used for the evaluation and the accuracy achieved is 78.41 %.

In [48], a CNN is emulated by a pre-processing of the input that includes filtering and splicing of contiguous constant-Q frames. Two different architectures are studied: one with the same number of neurons at each layer, and the other with a bottleneck shape. Pre-training is used to initialize the DNNs transforming it into a DBN. The training is carried out using SGD and BP with a cross-entropy loss function. For the classification, a softmax layer of size 25, which represent each of the major and minor chords plus an unknown chord position, is stacked on top of the DNN. Then, three classification options are presented: The first one is to pick the chord with the highest softmax layer's output value as the estimated chord; the second and third options are to introduce the output of the softmax layer into a SVM and a HMM classifiers, respectively. The data include 317 music recordings from the Beatles, RWC Pop, Zweieck and Queen datasets. As a data augmentation method, each frame of these 317 songs is used as a training sample, and thus, the dataset amounts to approximately 300k training samples and 76k test samples. The evaluation criterion used is the Weighted Chord Symbol Recall (WCSR), which computes the ratio of well classified frames with respect to the total frames. The best accuracy is achieved using the bottleneck architecture and the HMM classifier and rises up to a 91.9 %.

Concerning the key estimation task, in [51], two different types of beat-aligned input features are used: chroma and timbre features. In a first stage, each of these inputs is introduced into a different CNN, which includes a convolutional and a max-pooling layer. This way, no correlations between chroma and timbre features are learnt yet. In a second stage, the results of these two CNNs are used as features for a third CNN that can now discover dependencies between chroma and timbre features. A logistic regressor stacked on top of the whole structure is responsible for the classification of the network's output into a key. Two experiments are carried out: one with a random initialization of the weights using a Gaussian probability distribution and the other pre-training the network as a DBN. 250 music recordings from the Million Song Dataset, with automatically annotated, high confidence key ground truth, are extracted for each possible key root and used as dataset. The best accuracy result is 84.51 %.

2.6 Conclusions

After reviewing the most relevant literature about key estimation, we confirm the practical absence of any previous research about this topic using deep learning techniques. Only in [51] an attempt is carried out already obtaining state of the art results; however, the key ground truth is automatically annotated and the selected songs seem to have a clear key. Thus, we cannot confirm that the presented approach is a good starting point. Nonetheless, we can begin to list many ideas that could be worth trying in our investigation, such as combining both key and chord estimation tasks, using beat-aligned inputs or the possibility to artificially increase the amount of data.

3. DESIGN

This section presents the two approaches to the task of key estimation that we have implemented for this thesis: the Direct Key Estimation (DKE) and the Chord-Based Key Estimation (CBKE). We detail essential information such as their architectural characteristics, the type of input they accept, the output they produce, the way they are trained, etc. These two approaches, however, are not independent; on the contrary, the second one is an attempt to solve some of the problems and shortcomings of the first one and both of them are inspired by concepts that appeared in the review of the state of the art. Hence, it is an important goal of this section to explain the train of thought that we have followed to carry out this work and to relate it with what we have learnt from the analysed literature, as well as to justify the decisions that we have taken during the development process.

3.1 Direct Key Estimation

The first approach consists in a basic multi-layer perceptron (MLP) that can be described as an adaptive version of a template-based algorithm. We create it with our second goal in mind, i.e., we want to use it to learn more about how and what the network learns. Additionally, it has three other purposes: the first one is to compare its performance as a basic machine learning technique with that of the algorithm implemented in *Essentia*, which is template-based, in a similar way to [9]; the second purpose is to set a baseline for our second approach to surpass; and, finally, the last purpose is to check if processes such as data augmentation or custom weight initialization [59] might report benefits to the performance of neural networks.

a) Input

As explained in Section 2.1, in tonal music, key defines the relationship between pitch classes. In this first approach, just like in the template-based algorithms, we assume that the relationship between pitch classes, expressed as the particular distribution of their presence in a song, can define its key as well. Hence, we need to find the representation of a song that best conceives this information and, if possible, without adding any superfluous information such as the octave that the music is played in or the activity of frequencies that do not correspond to the musical notes. Our decision is to use the information conceived inside the chromagram as it is a well-known candidate for the key estimation task and meets all the stated requirements. However, what is most decisive is the way we present this information to the network.

Despite containing a lot of the necessary information for the key estimation task, the relationship between the chromagram and the key is obviously not univocal. The chromagram includes time information that is fairly independent from the key of the piece such as the order in which the notes are played at a chord time-scale. This represents a serious problem, as this superfluous information can create ambiguities that might confuse the network: Fig. 7 shows that two chromagrams that share the same key might have little in common. Moreover, similarities can be found in the chromagrams of songs with different key.

Figure 7 Chromagram of “I Saw Her Standing There” (top) and “Lovely Rita” from the Beatles (bottom). Both are written in the key of E major.

However, not all time information is irrelevant: chord progressions and cadences, for instance, are time-related cues tightly connected to the key of a song. Unfortunately, the only ground truth available for most of the datasets used for the key estimation task is the global key of each song. Thus, we suffer from a lack a local ground truth that could help us take advantage of this time information.

An intuitive solution to this problem could be to use a network similar to those used in computer vision tasks such as face recognition where a CNN with many filters scan the images in search of shapes that might resemble a face. In our case, we would pan over the chromagram trying to find time- and frequency-related cues about its key. However, this method has two flaws that make it unfeasible: in the first place, as mentioned before, two songs sharing the same key do not need to include similar shapes unlike faces do; and in the second place, neural networks require the input to be of a fixed size, while different songs rarely share durations. To solve that, we could just analyse an excerpt of this chroma, but having to decide on a fixed time range detracts robustness to the approach, as songs can modulate or establish their key in different moments. That is why, despite missing relevant time information, we decide to use as the input to the DKE network the 12-bin chromagram averaged in time for its whole duration, namely, the chroma.

b) Architecture

As a MLP, the architecture of the DKE network consists of an input, a hidden and an output layers. As mentioned in Section 2.3, in a neural network, each subsequent hidden layer represent a higher level of abstraction. Presenting the first hidden layer with information that is already directly related to key does not leave much room for a second one. We do not fix the number of neurons composing this layer because we use it as a parameter to find the configuration that offers the best performance. The output layer is composed by 24 neurons, each one of them representing one of the major and minor keys. Using a softmax function as the non-linear function of this layer allows it to produce a probability for each key. Obviously, the key represented by the neuron with the highest probability becomes the predicted key.

In a way, this approach is similar to a correlation-based method, as we expect each neuron to work as a template able to grasp characteristics of the inputted chroma. The difference lies in the adaptive capabilities of the neurons, which allows for a better adjustment to the particularities of a dataset.

c) Flow graph

In Fig. 8, we show the flow graph with the steps that the algorithm goes through. The process starts with the computation of the chromagram for each audio, which is later averaged in time for its whole duration resulting in the chroma representation of the audio. Before the training starts, all chromas are normalized to have 0 mean and unit variance and there is the possibility to increase the amount of training data using data augmentation. After that, the chromas of all the audio samples are used to train the network.

Figure 8 Flow graph with all the steps of the DKE algorithm.

3.2 Chord-Based Key Estimation

In the previous section, we stated that one of the restrictions that led us to average the chromagram in time for its whole duration, and therefore, to the omission of relevant time information for the estimation of key, was a lack of local ground truth that could help us make sense of this information. In this second approach we incorporate chord and beat information to work as local ground truth, allowing us to take advantage of some of the previously omitted time information. Specifically, the ground truth consists in a list that links each beat to the chord it belongs to. The chords are extracted from more accurate annotations [60] and mapped to 25 classes: the 24 major and minor chords and an extra class for unknown chords, which include, for instance, diminished and augmented chords or silences and noises.

To match this new ground truth, we take the DKE network as a basis, and choose to include a preliminary network devoted to the task of chord recognition. The purpose of the Chord Recognition Network (CRN) is to produce the chord information that is later processed and used to train and test the Key Estimation Network (KEN), which is the same as the DKE network, but with an input of size 24, and thus, more weights per neuron of the hidden layer. Our hypothesis is that with the chord information we will be able to produce an input that will enhance its performance. With this second approach, we are combining three of the concepts that we extracted from the study of the literature in Chapter 2: first, we use the task of chord recognition to facilitate the estimation of key; second, we use a beat-aligned input, which we detail in the next subsection; and third, we use a network to generate improved features rather than to solve a classification task.

a) Chord Recognition Network: input

A particularity of this network is that the input of the network is different depending on whether it is used for testing or for training. In the case of the testing set, the frequency information of the chromagram is averaged beat by beat using the beat ground truth and producing a beat-aligned chromagram. The reason why we choose to divide the chromagram using beat information is the close relationship between this time unit and musical content, e.g., in many occasions, chords change coinciding with the beat of the song. In the case of the input that forms the training set, there is a second averaging process that mixes contiguous beats belonging to the same chord for up to 4 beats resulting in a chord-aligned chromagram. Finally, the chord-aligned chromagram of all the songs are split chord by chord, and all chords are shuffled. Another way to understand the chord recognition network's input during training is as chromas including all the frequency information contained in the original chromagram for the duration of a single chord.

b) Chord Recognition Network: architecture

Just as it happens with the DKE network, to train the CRN, we present it with information that is already directly related to its output. This allows only for a hidden layer if we understand them as abstraction levels. Thus, we have again a multi-layer perceptron with a hidden layer of varying size, but this time with an output layer of 25 neurons: 24 for each major and minor chord and an additional neuron for unknown chords. Using a softmax non-linear function allows us to obtain a probability for each chord. The chord with the highest probability is the predicted chord.

It would clearly be unfair if we used the kind of input used during training in the testing phase, as it is created relying on the chord information that we aim to estimate. This is the reason why we use the beat-aligned chromagram. A problem arises, however, because beats do not necessarily contain all the frequency information of a chord, which is what we have trained the network with, and therefore, the recognition process becomes compromised. To solve that, we input the current beat to the network as well as its average with the following one, two and three beats, obtaining a total of four inputs, and thus, also four predictions. We assume that the prediction with the highest probability is the one that uses the same number of beats as the original chord contains. This chord is assigned to all the beats used in the prediction with the highest probability and these beats are skipped for the subsequent prediction. In the end, we obtain two sequences as long as beats has the song under analysis: one with the chord label of each beat and the other with the probability with which each chord has been predicted. We understand this probability as the confidence value of the corresponding chord.

c) Key Estimation Network: input

Using these two aforementioned sequences, we create the new input for the KEN. This input is a vector of length 24 with each position corresponding to one of the major and minor keys. The chords in the sequence sum its confidence value to all the keys it belongs to, and then, the value of each key is weighted by the presence of its tonic chord in the chord sequence. If the tonic chord of a key does not appear in this sequence, the

value of that key is set to 0 as the tonic chord of a key must appear in a song in that key. Finally, this data is normalized to 0 mean and unit variance and data augmentation is applied. This time, the shifting has to be done separately for the first and second half of the input.

e) Flow graph

In Fig. 9, we show the flow graph with the steps that the algorithm goes through. The process starts with the computation of the chromagram for each audio. Then, its beat-aligned version is computed and used to create the chord-aligned chromagram. The CRN is trained using all the chords in the chord-aligned chromagram, and tested with the beat-aligned chromagram. Finally, the data obtained through this testing is used to generate the input for the KEN. This input is normalized and the training split undergoes data augmentation.

Figure 9 Flow graph with all the steps of the CBKE algorithm.

4. EVALUATION

All the experiments that we present in this chapter have been carried out with one of our three goals in mind: to investigate what a network learns, to evaluate the performance of our algorithms, or to gather information that allows us to find out what is beneficial for the task of key estimation.

Additionally, unless specified otherwise, for the experiments in Sections 4.3 and 4.4, we use 10-fold cross-validation for 5 random seeds: 13, 42, 67, 80 and 95. The results for each seed are, averaged to obtain a more accurate evaluation of the performance of the algorithm. The training runs for 2000 epochs but early stopping is used to finish the training in case the learning process becomes stuck. The cost function to compute the error for each example inputted to the network during training is the categorical cross-entropy. The computation of the chroma is carried out using a Blackman-Harris 62-dB window and a frame and hop sizes of 8192 and 512 samples, respectively, to be consistent with the Essentia experiment. No dropout or momentum has been used and the batch size is always set to 1.

4.1 Methodology

To carry out these experiments we use 9 datasets, each of them containing samples of one of these three music styles: classical, pop-rock and electronic. The classicalDB dataset is composed of 884 recordings of many different authors; the bach-wtk1 dataset includes 48 pieces belonging to the Well-Tempered Klavier collection from J. S. Bach; the Beatles dataset contains the entirety of their discography, which amounts to 179 songs; the kf-pop dataset contributes with 152 well-known pop-rock songs of different authors; the Queen dataset is composed by 40 excerpts extracted from its Greatest Hits I album; the edm-925 includes 925 dance music samples; the gsbpk dataset contains 604 2-minutes long cuts of songs of several electronic music subgenres; 100 recordings from well-known artist, or remixes from them, form the kf-100 dataset; and finally the MIREX 05 dataset includes 96 classical piano wave files converted from midi.

For all the experiments that follow, we use 3 genre-specific datasets that result from the combination of 8 of the aforementioned datasets, i.e., all except for the MIREX 05 dataset. The genre-specific datasets are the classical, pop and electronic music datasets, with a total of 932, 371 and 1629 samples, respectively. Out of the 4 resulting datasets, only the MIREX dataset has a balanced amount of samples per key, as it would be a too restricting condition in terms of amount of data for the other datasets.

The annotations for all these musical material are stored in files that carry the name of the corresponding song and contain its key in the format “root mode”, where root is the tonic note and mode is either major or minor. The performance of all the evaluated algorithms is evaluated following the MIREX evaluation procedure for key detection, which gives a full point for well-classified instances, but also includes rewards for particular types of errors: if the estimated key is the fifth, the minor or major relative or the parallel of the actual key, the reward is 0.5, 0.3 and 0.2, respectively. Additionally, in all the result tables, we include the number of correct decisions and its percentage

over the total number of samples, i.e., the regular accuracy, and the absolute number and percentage over the total amount of mistakes of the different types of errors.

4.2 Template-based method baseline

The purpose of the first experiment is to set an accuracy baseline that the approaches proposed in this thesis need to surpass. To do this, we use the algorithm for key estimation that Essentia offers, which is template-based. In this experiment, we use 5 different types of profiles: tonictriad, thpcp, temperley, krumhansl and diatonic.

The algorithm has only 3 parameters: the frame size, the hop size and the profile type. To establish a baseline, we need to find the combination that provides the best accuracy. A first approach could be to carry out a grid search; unfortunately, the process would be very time consuming, and thus, we choose to reduce the number of cases by dividing it into two steps: firstly, we use fixed frame and hop sizes of 8192 and 512 samples, respectively, to check which profile works the best for each of the 4 datasets. Once the profiles are assigned, we fix the profile type and perform a grid search over the frame and hop sizes that take power of 2 values between 4096 to 32768 and 256 to 2048 samples, respectively. Table 2 shows the results of the best combination for each dataset. The chosen values for the frame and hop sizes finally coincide with the initial ones, i.e., 8192 and 512 samples.

Table 2 Results of the Essentia baseline experiment.

Dataset	Accuracy (MIREX)	Correct decisions	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors	Key profile
MIREX '05	90.31 %	82/96 85.42 %	6/14 42.86 %	5/14 35.71 %	1/14 7.14 %	2/14 14.28 %	Krumhansl
Classical	74.8 %	643/932 68.99 %	69/289 23.88%	44/289 15.22 %	32/289 11.07%	144/289 49.83%	Krumhansl
Pop	65.61 %	227/371 61.19 %	12/144 8.33 %	26/144 18.06 %	13/144 9.03 %	93/144 64.58 %	Temperley
Electronic	47.25 %	667/1629 40.95 %	61/962 6.34 %	183/962 18.92 %	88/962 9.15 %	630/962 65.49 %	Diatonic

We can see that Table 2 presents very uncompensated results: the performance of the algorithm surpasses 90 % accuracy for the MIREX datasets, but it does not reach 50 % for the electronic music dataset. This is a clear example of the limitations of the template-based algorithms exposed in Section 2.2: if a template for a particular musical genre does not exist or you do not have access to it for any other reason, the performance of the algorithm might be seriously affected. As mentioned before, the DKE network works in a similar way to the template-based methods such as this one; thus, this is a good chance to see if its adaptive capacity allows for an improvement in terms of accuracy.

4.3 Direct Key Estimation

a) Results

Two of the purposes of the DKE network are to compare the performance of template-based and machine learning algorithms and to set a baseline for the CBKE approach. For both of these tasks, we need to find the combination of parameters, for which the best accuracy is achieved. An early inspection of the impact over the training process of a dropout probability higher than 0 is detrimental, while the batch size for which the best results are obtained is 1. These values are reasonable as our network and datasets are quite small, and thus, not very prone to overfitting, which is what these parameters aim to neutralize. Consequently, for this experiment, the only variable parameters are the learning rate and the number of neurons of the hidden layer, over which we run a grid search. The results of this process for each of the datasets are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Results of the DKE approach evaluation.

Dataset	Accuracy (MIREX)	Correct decisions	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors	Num. filters / lr
MIREX 05	65.79 %	52.8/96 55 %	9/52.8 17.05 %	20/52.8 37.88 %	0.6/52.8 1.14 %	13.6/52.8 25.76 %	120/0.001
Classical	78.67 %	234.4 / 932 74.84 %	34.6/ 234.4 14.76 %	44.2/ 234.4 18.86 %	25.2/ 234.4 10.75 %	130.4/ 234.4 55.63 %	168/0.001
Pop	68.05 %	224.8/ 371 60.59 %	25.4/ 146.2 17.37 %	36.2/ 146.2 24.76 %	20.8/ 146.2 14.23 %	63.8/ 146.2 43.64 %	168/0.01
Elect.	71.33 %	1086.4/ 1629 66.69 %	90.8/ 542.6 16.73 %	51.6/ 542.6 9.51 %	73/ 542.6 13.45 %	327.2/ 542.6 60.3 %	180/0.001

Comparing the results in Table 3 with those obtained by the Essentia algorithm, we observe a timid improvement for the classical and pop datasets. However, the adaptive nature of the machine learning approaches clearly provides much better results for the electronic dataset. Nonetheless, the necessity for bigger amounts of data is evident in the case of the MIREX dataset. We address this last issue in the next subsection.

b) Data augmentation

One of the most problematic handicaps that we encounter is that the datasets we use are rather small and unbalanced in the number of examples per class, which leads to an uneven training of the different classes. The worst case would be to have no training examples for a particular class in the current fold because they are all in the testing or validation sets. This strongly harms the performance of the neural network.

Even though the results obtained in the last experiment are already better than the Essentia baseline for two of the datasets, we considered that they still have much room for improvement if we take care of the lack of data and its unbalanced number of

examples per key. That is why we decide to artificially increase the amount of data using data augmentation in a very similar way as done in [50].

An advantage of using chroma as the input to our network is that data augmentation can be easily applied just by rotating it in the frequency axis due to its frequency invariant nature. For instance, if a chroma input has the C major key as its ground truth, for each shifting of one position, the key increases one semitone maintaining always the same mode, i.e., from C major to C# major. This has the advantage of increasing 12 times the initial amount of training data and, additionally, we achieve a balance in the number of instances per class. We are aware that the necessary transformations of the original sound to produce a shifted chroma would introduce serious changes to it. However, we do not need to pay attention to that as we are sure that the new version, as modified as it might be, has a key as recognizable as its chroma. Additionally, if an actual song has produced the original chroma, there is no reason to think that a different original song could produce the shifted chroma.

The effectivity of the application of this kind of data augmentation is shown in Table 4. It is clear that it does not introduce irrelevant or incorrect information that might harm the performance of the algorithm. On the contrary, the increased amount of data and its balance in terms of examples per class boosts it in the case of the smaller datasets, i.e., the MIREX dataset, for which the accuracy surpasses that of the Essentia experiment, and the pop dataset, for which the improvement is not as strong but still considerable. However, the classical and electronic datasets do not undergo any significant changes probably due to the fact that they already had a sufficient amount of samples for every key.

Table 4 Results of the DKE approach evaluation with data augmentation.

Dataset	Accuracy (MIREX)	Correct decisions	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors	Num. filters / lr
MIREX 05	91.52 %	85/96 88.54 %	2.4/11 21.82 %	5.2/11 47.27 %	1/11 9.09 %	2.4/11 21.82 %	120/0.001
Classical	78.26 %	696.8 / 932 74.76 %	31.4 / 235.2 13.35 %	36.4 / 235.2 15.48 %	30 / 235.2 12.76 %	137.4 / 235.2 58.42 %	168/0.001
Pop	75.68 %	256.2 / 371 69.06 %	19.6 / 114.8 17.07 %	27.6 / 114.8 24.04 %	21.6 / 114.8 18.82 %	46 / 114.8 40.07 %	168/0.001
Elect.	71.19 %	1083.8 / 1629 66.53 %	88.2 / 545.2 16.18 %	54 / 545.2 9.9 %	78.2 / 545.2 14.34 %	324.8 / 545.2 59.57 %	180/0.001

c) Custom weights initialization

By initializing the weights of the neurons that form the hidden layer in a deterministic way, in this experiment we impose a certain learning path to the network in an attempt to achieve results that surpass those obtained by a random initialization. Our hypothesis is that the intensity with which each chord is present in the chroma of a song represents valuable information to estimate the key of the song; therefore, a network that is able to

evaluate this presence has a better chance to predict it correctly. That is why we initialize the weights of a 24-neuron hidden layer to resemble the major and minor chord profiles. We present the results of this experiment in Table 5.

Table 5 Results of the custom weights initialization experiment. The accuracy values presented are computed using the MIREX scoring system.

Dataset	Custom init. 24 neurons	Random init. 24 neurons	Best Accuracy
MIREX 05	91.84 %	90.62 %	91.52 %
Classical	77.66 %	77.63 %	78.26 %
Pop	74.17 %	73.97 %	75.68 %
Electronic	70.81 %	71.02 %	71.19 %

Even though the performance using custom initialization is better than using random initialization, the largest difference is only around 1 %, which is not very significant, and all results are inferior to those achieved using a larger number of randomly initialized neurons. Actually, what is significant is the similarity of the accuracy obtained for both cases. This made us consider the possibility that the randomly initialized network could be already learning something close to a chord profile on its own.

In Fig. 10, we show the weights of the hidden-layer neurons after training for the custom (left) and random (right) cases, and the colour map in the left-most part of the image. Each of the 24 columns contains the 12 weights by which each neuron multiplies the input chroma, i.e., their particular template. In the custom case, the first 12 columns correspond to the major chords and the other to the minor chords. The highlighted diagonals are the values that we have forced with the custom initialization, with the longest diagonal being the tonic of each chord and the others corresponding to the major or minor third and the perfect fifth. Surprisingly, we can appreciate how some of the high valued diagonals and specially the one belonging to the tonic of the chords appear also in the case of the random initialization.

Figure 10 Weights, after training, of the hidden-layer neurons for the custom initialization (left) and the random initialization (right).

With this experiment we conclude, first, that at least for a simple case, it is possible to create a network that allows us to understand what it is learning. Furthermore, we

realize that the network has learnt something musically meaningful as it is able to evaluate the presence of the major and minor chords in the input chroma and combine this information to output a key prediction. We have achieved that by constraining the information we allow the network to see and the way it must learn it, i.e., choosing the appropriate input and network dimensions, respectively.

d) Error analysis

An important part of the evaluation of any algorithm is the analysis of the mistakes it makes in order to extract conclusions about its behaviour and how it can be improved. In this subsection, we want to go more into detail about the reasons why these errors happen by examining the characteristics of the songs that produce them. For this task, we choose to use the Beatles dataset for three reasons: the first one is that with 179 samples it is small enough for us to check the errors case by case; the second one is that it is the only dataset for which we have chord and local key information, which can help us to better understand the DKE mistakes; and finally, it is the dataset that we use to evaluate our second network, and thus, we want to have as much detailed information about it as possible. The results presented in this section are for songs used only for testing. Luckily, by using k-fold cross-validation all the songs of the dataset are used for this purpose.

The first thing we realize while comparing key and chord annotations and listening to the songs that produce errors is that the key annotations are not correct for seven of the songs of the dataset. The correction of these annotations affect not only to the testing but also to the training of the network improving its performance. All the results presented in this section have been computed after these corrections. Table 6 presents the changes that we have made.

Table 6 Key ground truth corrections in the Beatles dataset.

Song	Former key	Correct key
Ob-la-di, Ob-la-da	B major	Bb major
Piggies	A major	Ab major
Yellow Submarine	G major	F# major
Across The Universe	D major	C# major
P.S. I Love You	D minor	D major
Revolution 1	B major	A major
Here Comes The Sun	A minor	A major

The Beatles dataset contains two special types of songs based on their key: those that have more than one local key, which we call multi-key and amount up to 21 samples; and those that have a key mode that is neither major nor minor such as the mixolydian, dorian or aeolian modes, which include 7 samples. In both of these cases a mapping is necessary to use them with our approach, but this mapping introduces errors that hinder its performance. In Table 7, we can see that the impact of the multi-key type of songs is

much stronger than that of the non-major/minor case. Especially significant is the comparison between the percentage of the total number of samples that a particular type represents (last column of Table 7) and the percentage of the total number of errors that correspond to this type (third column of Table 7). This ratio reveals that the type that is harder to estimate is the multi-key type. The percentages in the second column of Table 7 point in the same way.

Table 7 Error statistics by key type. These results have been obtained using the DKE network with 180 neurons, a learning rate of 0.001 and a single random seed. They are superior to the average.

Key type	Num. of error / Num. of samples	Num. of errors / Total errors	Num. of samples / Total samples
Multi-key	11/21 52.38 %	11/42 26.19 %	21/179 11.73 %
Non-major/minor	1/7 14.29 %	1/42 2.38 %	7/179 3.91 %
Single	30/151 19.87 %	30/42 71.43 %	151/179 84.46 %

These results shouldn't be surprising; the chroma produced by averaging the frequency content of a song containing parts in different keys is not necessarily similar to any other single-key chroma. Actually, the task of predicting the key of this type of songs based on the frequency content makes no sense, as the key might have been assigned taking into account other, more abstract or formal reasons.

Table 8 Types of errors for the single-key type of songs.

Key type	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors
Single	6/30 (20 %)	4/30 (13.33 %)	2/30 (6.67 %)	18/30 (60 %)

In Table 8, we show the distribution of the errors only for the single-key type of songs as the fifth, relative and parallel error categories have no meaning for multi-key and non-major/minor songs. However, the errors that fall into these categories usually have a clear explanation; thus, we consider the non-rewarded mistakes to be of much more interest. These errors normally happen due to the presence of chords that do not belong to the key of the song, which might already imply subtle key modulations, or because a chord that belongs to the key has a much stronger presence compared with the tonic chord. In the most extreme cases, the key of the song can be very ambiguous, which clashes with the inflexibility of a unique global key ground truth and the simplicity of template-based methods.

e) Cross-evaluation

Despite being able to adapt, to a certain extent, to the characteristics of each dataset, machine learning methods still suffer from the limitation that training them with

examples of a particular genre supposes. In this experiment, we want to analyse how a network trained with one of the datasets work when tested against the other three. This can give us information about what datasets allow the network to generalize better and also about the similarity between datasets. The results shown in Table 9 are computed using the best network parameters possible for each training dataset.

Table 9 Results of the cross-evaluation experiment. Rows indicate the dataset used for training and columns the dataset used for testing. All testing datasets were used against a DKE network initialized with the parameters that offered the best performance with the dataset used for training.

Train / Test dataset	MIREX 05	Classical	Pop	Electronic
MIREX 05	93.3 % (90.56 %)	69.48 % (64.27 %)	52.85 % (48.38 %)	38.75 % (31.94 %)
Classical	83.33 % (75.16 %)	78.86 % (75.32 %)	55.75 % (51.50 %)	41.68 % (34.52 %)
Pop	85.44 % (77.22 %)	71.65 % (61.59 %)	76.29 % (70.32 %)	59.36 % (51.68 %)
Electronic	59.28 % (44.18 %)	47.43 % (36.04 %)	47.96 % (35.56 %)	71.53 % (66.91 %)

A very interesting conclusion of this experiment is that the generalization relationship between two networks when tested with the others training set is not reciprocal. We identify two factors that influence the generalization capacity of a network when tested with another dataset: the similarity between the examples contained in the dataset it has been trained with, and the similarity of these examples with the testing dataset. This way, in the case of two similar datasets in terms of genre such as the MIREX and the classical music datasets, the network trained with the latest, which include more varied examples, is the one that generalizes better. We also observe that the network trained with the pop music dataset, which contains some songs that present characteristics related to the electronic music is the only one that surpasses 50 % accuracy when tested with the electronic dataset. In fact, this network is the one that generalizes better for all the other datasets, while the network trained with the electronic music dataset is the worst, probably due to the scarce similarity between the musical genres. Finally, the dataset that offers an easier generalization is the MIREX dataset.

As a complementary experiment, we combine all datasets to train a single network and compare its performance with the weighted average of the individual results. Table 10 shows that the results are similar but a bit inferior for the combined datasets. Training with very different information probably does not allow the network to pay attention to details that it can grasp when trained dataset by dataset. Additionally, training with individual datasets provides much more flexibility in terms of parameter adjustment.

Table 10 Results of the combination of all datasets for training and testing.

All datasets	Weighted average of dataset results
71.46 % (66.18 %)	74.56 % (70.07 %)

f) Direct Key Estimation and SVM baselines

This experiment is simply devoted to provide the CBKE approach with two baselines to compare with. The first one is set using the DKE network and the second one with a SVM. As explained in Section 3.2, our second approach requires both beat and chord ground truth, and the only dataset that offers this kind of information is the Beatles dataset; this is why we are limited to it for all the experiments related to the CBKE. To be as fair as possible, the same processes of normalization and data augmentation that we apply to the input in the CBKE approach are applied also for the computation of these baselines. As indicated in Table 11, the performance of the SVM is superior to the DKE approach.

Table 11 Results of the second approach baselines. For the SVM experiment we have used the scikit-learn library with the default parameters, except for $C = 1.4$.

Method	Accuracy (MIREX)	Correct decisions	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors	Num. filters / lr
DKE	77.6 %	131/179 73.18 %	9.6/48 19.51 %	6.2/48 12.92 %	5.6/48 11.67 %	26.6/48 55.42 %	180/0.001
SVM	81.58 %	137.6/179 76.87 %	11.4/41.4 27.54 %	7.2/41.4 17.39 %	3/41.4 7.25 %	19.8/41.4 47.83 %	-

4.4 Chord-Based Key Estimation

a) Results

Looking at Table 12, it is clear that the chord recognition network is far from offering state of the art results for its task with an accuracy around 60 %. However, the percentage is 20 % higher if we only consider the chords predicted with a probability value over 90 %. This means that using this probability as a confidence value for the chords is a good idea. Additionally, the possibility arises to use only the chords with a high enough confidence value for the computation of the input of the key estimation network in the manner explained in Subsection 3.2.c. This way, we would ensure that the chords used are less prone to errors; however, depending on the probability threshold, they might be too few and not necessarily the most representative of the key of the song, and thus, they might produce an input that does not match the key ground truth.

Table 12 Results of the CRN network. P is the probability with which the chords are predicted. In the first column all chords are included. The batch size used is 10.

Accuracy	Accuracy P > 90 %	Accuracy P > 80 %	Accuracy P > 70 %	Accuracy P > 60 %	Accuracy P > 50 %	Num. filters / lr / batch size
60.09 %	82.52 %	75.78 %	71.14 %	67.18 %	64.03 %	120 / 0.001 / 10

Probably, a compromise between the confidence value and the number of chords used for the creation of the input can be reached, but we have decided to use them all. We have taken this decision knowing that each value of the key estimation network input is weighted by the relative presence of the tonic chord of the corresponding key; hence, reducing the impact of erroneous chords. To produce the results in Table 13, the input data for training has been artificially augmented and normalized just like we explained in the Subsection 3.2.c.

Comparing the results in Table 13 with the baselines in Table 11, we can conclude that, despite introducing erroneous information due to the errors of the CRN network, the addition of chord data together with its post-processing allows the KEN to surpass the performance of the DKE network. However, we cannot reach the accuracy that the SVM achieves.

Table 13 Results of the KEN with the input generated by the CRN network using all chords.

Accuracy (MIREX)	Correct decisions	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors	Num. filters / lr
81.27 %	136.6/179 76.32 %	12.2/42.4 28.77 %	6.4/42.4 15.09 %	4.4/42.4 10.38 %	19.4/42.4 45.75 %	120/0.001

b) Glass ceiling for network performance

Taking into account that the focus of this thesis is not chord recognition but key estimation, we carry out this experiment to find out what is the best performance that the key estimation network can offer without being constrained by the mistakes of the chord recognition network. To do so, we just need to skip the chord recognition phase and compute the input for the key estimation network using the chord annotations. This way, we are pretending that the chord recognition network has an accuracy of 100 % and predicts each chord with a confidence value of 1. Table 14 shows these hypothetical results.

Table 14 Results of the KEN for the input computed from the chord annotations.

Accuracy (MIREX)	Correct decisions	Fifth errors	Relative errors	Parallel errors	Other errors	Num. filters / lr
87.96 %	151.2/179 84.45 %	10.6/27.8 38.13 %	3.2/27.8 11.51 %	0.2/27.8 0.72 %	13.8/27.8 49.64 %	180/0.001

In Table 14, we observe an accuracy improvement of around 10 % and 6 % from the baselines set with the DKE network and the SVM, respectively, in Subsection 4.3.f; and also 6 % from the actual performance of the CBKE network, shown in Table 13. This last difference represents the degradation caused by the errors of the CRN. Additionally, we want to highlight the practical absence of parallel errors. We believe this is partly due to the process of generation of the input for the KEN, which includes weighting each of its values by the relative presence of the tonic chord of the corresponding key as explained in Subsection 3.2.c.

c) Error analysis

To know more about the behaviour of this network we analyse the mistakes it makes just like we did with the first approach. We see many similarities, specifically, the non-major / minor error is still present and produced by the same song and the single-key errors come from a very similar set of samples and for the same reasons. Focusing on the differences between both approaches, in Table 15, we show that the CBKE has been able to reduce the multi-key errors in almost 30 %, going from 11 to 8, but they are still the main problem.

Table 15 Error statistics by key type. These results have been obtained using the KEN, with a hidden layer of 120 neurons, a learning rate of 0.001 and a single random seed.

Key type	Num. of error / Num. of samples	Num. of errors / Total errors	Num. of samples / Total samples
Multi-key	8/21 38.09 %	8/41 19.51 %	21/179 11.73 %
Non-major / minor	1/7 14.29 %	1/41 2.44 %	7/179 3.91 %
Single	32/151 21.19 %	32/42 76.19 %	151/179 84.46 %

5. CONCLUSIONS

Regarding the first goal, through the several experiments that we have carried out, we have been able to test the suitability of many of the ideas that we extracted from the review of the literature to our particular case. For instance, we have observed a good response of our approaches to the data augmentation and balancing process, especially when using the smaller datasets. Also, we have realized that the incorporation of the task of chord recognition to the process of key estimation reports a significant accuracy improvement, despite the possible introduction of a certain amount of incorrect data, effectively proving that the combination of different MIR tasks can be helpful as mentioned in Section 2.2. We want to highlight that the main reason for this improvement is the generation, through feature engineering using the CRN and the post-processing of its output, of a new set of features that, unlike chroma, implicitly include temporal information. On the downside, we have not been able to move away from the template-based methods and their inherent loss of valuable time-related information.

From the point of view of the second goal, we have confirmed that it is possible for a small network to learn something musically meaningful given the appropriate input and architectural constraints. Specifically, after the training, our network could evaluate and combine the presence of the major and minor chords in the chroma of a song to take a decision about its key.

As for the third goal, we have clearly outperformed the state of the art results for the template-based methods. Moreover, by adding the chord recognition task and beat information into the process, we have almost reached the level of a machine learning techniques as powerful as the SVM.

6. FUTURE WORK

To finish this work, we want to expose the general aspects of a hypothetical third approach that could solve some of the problems that have appeared in the previous two. Probably, its most important characteristic should be to distance itself from the template-based methods. A way to do this is to incorporate the temporal variable into the algorithm, for instance, using a RNN. With this type of network, instead of inputting the frequency information all at once as we do with the chroma, we could provide the beat- or chord-aligned chromagram one frame at a time in order for the network to find additional cues about the key of the song in the form of temporal patterns such as cadences or usual chord sequences. An advantage of the RNNs over the CNNs is that they can process inputs of variable length with the usage of masks; this would allow us to input the whole song eliminating the necessity to cut it into parts of the same duration. Additionally, RNNs can output either a decision at each time step or a single decision for the complete input sequence, allowing for local and global key estimation.

Using LSTM units, which solves the problem of the vanishing/exploding gradient that appears for regular RNN, or trying other optimization algorithms such as ADAM could be ways to boost the performance of this network; however, we believe that the strongest improvement has to come from the annotations: if we want the network to actually learn about key, we should teach it to interpret tonal music like humans do. A way to do this could be to create a different kind of annotations that, for instance, classified each chord by its intention or role inside the piece. Maybe this way, the RNN would link this intention not only to the frequencies of the current chord but to their relationship with the frequencies of previous and future chords. To put a simple example, the network could learn to assign the dominant role to chords including the 7th note that later fall to the tonic chord.

7. REPRODUCIBILITY

The introduction of Chapter 4, in combination with the subsection of each experiment, contains the necessary information about the parameters used to carry out all the experiments in this work. Additionally, in order to allow for the reproducibility of these experiments, we have uploaded the code of our two approaches as well as a document explaining how to use them and the required data to the following public repositories:

- Direct Key Estimation:
 - https://bitbucket.org/bmelcat/mt2016_keg2
- Chord-Based Key Estimation:
 - Chord Recognition Network: https://bitbucket.org/bmelcat/mt2016_crn
 - Key Estimation Network: https://bitbucket.org/bmelcat/mt2016_ken

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